

Origami Frustration and Its Influence on Energy Landscapes of Origami Assemblies

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Harnessing instabilities of multicomponent multistable structural assemblies can potentially lead to scalable and reversible functionalities, which can be enhanced by exploring frustration. For instance, standard Kresling origami cells exhibit non-tunable intrinsic energy landscapes determined by their geometry and material properties, limiting their adaptability after fabrication. To overcome this limitation, we introduce frustration to enable fine-tuning of the energy landscape and resulting deformation states. By prestressing the Kresling cell by means of special springs with individual control, we induce either global or localized (i.e., crease level) frustration, which allows changing the energy barrier (cell or assembly). We investigate the mechanical behavior of frustrated Kresling assemblies, both theoretically and experimentally, under various loading and boundary conditions. Our findings reveal that changing the frustration state leads to precise control of folding sequences, enabling previously inaccessible folding paths. The proposed concept paves the way for innovative applications in mechanical metamaterials and other fields requiring highly programmable and reconfigurable systems.

Geometrical frustration | Origami | Kresling pattern | Energy landscape

Reconfigurable assemblies consist of engineered macroscopic nonlinear structures undergoing large deformations. The behavior of the assemblies depends on the material properties and geometrical nonlinearity of the local unit cells. Classic nonlinear cells, such as snap-through beams (1, 2), and buckling-driven continuum elements (3, 4), have been explored in applications, including energy absorption (5, 6), soft robotic actuators (7, 8), non-commutative response (9), wave propagation (10), acoustic metamaterials (11, 12), and soft matter undergoing dramatic shape changes (13, 14). More recently, origami-inspired geometry has enriched the design space of the nonlinear unit cells such as Kresling (15–20), square-twist (21, 22), Waterbomb (23, 24), and Miura-Ori variations (25–27), and curved folds (28, 29). Furthermore, the non-rigid origami assemblies have enabled finite deformation for applications involving shape morphing (30–32) and controllable energy landscape (32–34). The aforementioned reconfigurable assemblies assume a pre-defined deformation path; thus, the nonlinear properties, e.g., the shape of the energy landscape and the instability behavior, are non-tunable after fabrication. On the other hand, reprogrammable structures enable continuously variable elastic modulus via changing the configurational state of local units (35), e.g., heights of the elastic shells (36), rotation angles of the gears (37), and rolling motion of the cams (38). A limited number of studies have applied this reprogrammability concept for assemblies with tunable instability behaviors (39, 40), e.g., switch between monostable and bistable responses. The switching behavior is achieved by actuating two distinct topological states of a local unit. However, the limited local states restrict the number of global deformation paths, which makes it difficult to reprogram the energy barrier of the assembly continuously.

Here, we introduce geometrical frustration (41) into the origami-inspired assemblies, together with novel experimental fixtures (e.g., free-rotating and free-translating), to achieve continuous energy landscape reprogrammability. The geometrical frustration is embedded within the origami cells by means of three mechanisms: global stretch, global rotation, and crease (local) stretch (Fig. 1A). Each mechanism integrates shell-based origami with special spring elements, which introduce prestress into the frustrated origami cell. The prestress level of the frustrated model is continuously adjustable by controlling the spring properties, i.e., stretching/rotating direction and magnitude. The frustrated assemblies, with tunable prestresses, enable one to engineer the energy landscape of multiple stable states on the fly. We achieve unprecedented folding paths, otherwise infeasible (Fig. 1B, Movie S1). This finding paves the way for potential

Significance Statement

Frustration: detrimental or desirable? Sometimes detrimental, but sometimes desirable to achieve new functionalities of nonrigid multistable origami structures. It provides the means to augment the energy landscape of such structures as it can be tailored to the features of the geometry of the origami unit cell and the frustration type. By equipping the cell with special, controllable, elastic springs, fine-tune control over energy barriers is enabled, facilitating precise folding sequences. Experiments demonstrate that activation or deactivation of the frustration can enhance the programmability of a multicell origami array, unlocking otherwise unfeasible folding paths. With potential impact in fields such as mechanical computing and non-commutative state transition, this approach offers possibilities for scalable and adaptable structures with high tunability.

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Standard Kresling cell assembly

Fig. 1. Standard and geometrically frustrated origami assemblies with tunable energy landscapes and folding paths. (A) Top: Schematic of the standard Kresling origami (brown) and its intrinsic energy landscapes. The symbols u and φ denote displacement and twist angle, respectively. Bottom: Schematics of the frustrated models (orange) with three types of prestress: (i) global stretch, (ii) global rotation, and (iii) crease stretch (local) and their tunable energy landscapes. The symbols ℓ_e and η_e denote the length of the axial spring and the rotating angle of the torsional spring, respectively. (B) Top: an infeasible folding path using the standard Kresling assembly. Here, ΔU_1 and ΔU_2 denote the intrinsic energy barriers of the origami cells made of different materials. Bottom: frustrated assembly achieving an unprecedented folding deformation. Here, ΔU_{fru} and U_{spr} denote the energy barrier of the frustrated model and the elastic energy stored in the torsional spring element, respectively. Insets show the rotational test setup with the free-translation fixture and experimental data of twist angle φ versus torque T .

applications in reconfigurable mechanical metamaterials and non-commutative state transitions.

Results

Theory of geometrical frustration. Starting from the theoretical modeling of the Kresling origami, which describes its mechanics through an elastic energy dependent on two independent variables, displacement u and twist angle φ , we develop an enhanced model for the frustrated system. We write the total elastic energy of the frustrated model, $U_{\text{fru}}(u, \varphi)$, as follows:

$$U_{\text{fru}}(u, \varphi) = U_{\text{spr}}(u, \varphi) + U(u, \varphi), \quad [1]$$

where $U(u, \varphi)$ is the elastic energy of the standard Kresling cell (42), and $U_{\text{spr}}(u, \varphi)$ denotes the elastic energy stored in the prestressed springs, which embed frustration into the origami cell. The five-term elastic energy of the standard cell is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} U(u, \varphi) = & \frac{1}{2} n_b k_{s,b} (b(u, \varphi) - b_0)^2 \\ & + \frac{1}{2} n_c k_{s,c} (c(u, \varphi) - c_0)^2 \\ & + \frac{1}{2} n_a k_{r,a} (\delta_a(u, \varphi) - \delta_{a0})^2 \\ & + \frac{1}{2} n_b k_{r,b} (\delta_b(u, \varphi) - \delta_{b0})^2 \\ & + \frac{1}{2} n_c k_{r,c} (\delta_c(u, \varphi) - \delta_{c0})^2. \end{aligned} \quad [2]$$

We offer a detailed explanation of the material parameters $k_{s,i}$ ($i = b$ and c) and $k_{r,i}$ ($i = a, b$, and c), the geometric parameters b, c, δ_i ($i = a, b$, and c), and the parameters n_i ($i = a, b$, and c) in the SI Appendix, section 1, Fig. S1, and Table S1.

Using the principle of minimum total potential energy, the equilibrium conditions for axial and torque loading can be derived with Eq.1. Specifically, the axial force and torque can be calculated as follows:

$$F_{\text{fru}}(u, \varphi) = \frac{\partial U_{\text{spr}}(u, \varphi)}{\partial u} + \frac{\partial U(u, \varphi)}{\partial u}, \quad [3]$$

$$T_{\text{fru}}(u, \varphi) = \frac{\partial U_{\text{spr}}(u, \varphi)}{\partial \varphi} + \frac{\partial U(u, \varphi)}{\partial \varphi}. \quad [4]$$

Here, the expression of $U_{\text{spr}}(u, \varphi)$ depends on the prestressed spring mechanism of interest. We present three types of frustrated models, i.e., global stretch, global rotation, and crease stretch, in the following sessions (see details of theoretical formulation in SI Appendix, section 1).

Global stretch. This model involves a single deformed spring element inserted in the origami and aligned with its central axis. In the theoretical analysis, the initial state of the spring can be either extended or compressed, providing the origami with tunable prestress properties. The extended spring deforms the origami cell in the folding direction, while the compressed spring stretches the unit in the deploying direction. The prestressed spring is coupled with the origami

cell to achieve a new equilibrium stage, denoted as the frustrated mode. The resulting energy landscape of the frustrated mode is programmable by adjusting the elastic energy stored in the spring element, defined as follows:

$$U_{\text{spr}}(u, \varphi) = \frac{1}{2}k_{s,e}(\Delta\ell_e - u)^2, \quad [5]$$

where $k_{s,e}$ and $\Delta\ell_e$ are the stiffness and length change of the spring element embedded in the frustrated Kresling cell.

Global rotation. This model takes advantage of the rotational degree of freedom of the Kresling origami and embeds torsional prestress into the unit cell. The prestress level is controlled by a torsional spring integrated with the origami cell. The spring rotates the undeformed cell and reaches a new equilibrium state with prestresses. The spring enables two types of prestresses, which are defined as positive and negative. The positive prestress rotates the cell in the same direction as its intrinsic twisting direction, while the negative prestress rotates the unit in the opposite direction. The elastic energy functional for the torsional springs is defined as follows:

$$U_{\text{spr}}(u, \varphi) = \frac{1}{2}k_{r,e}(\Delta\eta_e - \varphi)^2, \quad [6]$$

where $k_{r,e}$ and $\Delta\eta_e$ are the stiffness and rotating angle change of the torsional spring integrated in the frustrated model.

Crease (local) stretch. This model embeds prestressed springs along the mountain creases (local) of the origami cell to frustrate the system. Those local spring elements deform the unit into a new stable state with a non-zero base energy. The magnitude of the base energy and energy barrier of the frustrated model are tunable by controlling the elastic energy stored in the springs, defined as follows:

$$U_{\text{spr}}(u, \varphi) = \frac{1}{2}n_e k_{s,e}(b(u, \varphi) - b_0 + \Delta\ell_e)^2, \quad [7]$$

where n_e is the number of the stretching springs along the mountain creases ($n_e = 3$ in this paper), $b(u, \varphi)$ is the length of the mountain crease, b_0 is the initial length of the mountain crease at the undeformed state of the Kresling cell, and $\Delta\ell_e$ is the length change of the spring element.

Parametric study. The frustrated cells integrate three types of prestressed models into the standard Kresling origami. Eqs. 5-7 show that the elastic energy stored in the prestressed springs is controlled by its deformation. Thus, we can navigate the energy landscape by varying the length change $\Delta\ell_e$ and rotating angle change $\Delta\eta_e$ of the spring elements, respectively (Fig. 2). We refer to SI Appendix, Table S2 for the selection of parameters. Recall that we denote the positive prestress as deforming the origami cell in the folding direction, while the negative prestress deforms the unit in the deploying direction. Both positive and negative prestress drive the undeformed origami into new equilibrium states with non-zero base energy, and the corresponding energy landscapes are tunable. For instance, the global stretch model enables two frustrated modes: one with negative prestress and the other one with positive prestress (Fig. 2A). Both modes have non-zero base energy at the initial stable state; however, in the negative mode, the energy at the second stable state always increases, while for the positive mode, the base energy of

the 2nd stable state can either increase or remain unchanged depending on the given length change in the prestressed spring. Note that the base energy of the 2nd stable state for the positive mode is similar to the base energy of the standard Kresling. This behavior is due to the frustrating setup used in the positive mode, where the elongated spring becomes invalid after returning to its original length. By contrast, the springs are always compressed in the negative mode. Thus, the resulting energy landscapes for the two modes, negative and positive, can be quite different. This finding holds for results obtained using two independent loading conditions: compression with free-rotation (Fig. 2B-left) and torsion with free-translation (Fig. 2B-right). Notably, by controlling the level of prestress in the negative mode, we can switch the instability behavior from bistable to monostable, as shown in Fig. 2B (Top: two orange curves). Another unique feature is the capability to continuously program the energy barrier of the cell with frustration. Here, the energy barrier is defined as the difference between the local maximum on the landscape and the initial base energy. Fig. 2C shows the theoretical energy barrier as a function of the stretching length of the prestressed spring. Moreover, the curve shows a smooth transition between the negative mode and the positive mode. This result highlights the capability of the frustrated model to achieve fine-tuned control over energy barriers.

Another frustration model we investigate is the global rotation (Fig. 2D), which also has two modes similar to the global stretch, i.e., negative mode and positive mode. The negative mode integrates a prestressed torsional spring rotating the origami opposite to the twisting direction of the cell while it folds. The positive mode embeds a torsional spring that rotates the origami along the same direction while the cell folds. By controlling the prestress level of the torsional springs, we can achieve non-zero bases for the initial stable states of the cell. Further, the shape of the energy landscape can be programmed as shown in Fig. 2E. As a result, the global rotation-induced frustrated cell has switchable instabilities, i.e., monostable or bistable behavior. Notably, the energy barrier between the local maximum and the initial base energy can be continuously tunable as shown in Fig. 2F.

The last frustration model we investigate is the crease stretch shown in Fig. 2G. The prestressed springs are located along some mountain creases due to fabrication considerations, as shown in the later experimental validation sessions. The crease stretch has two prestressed modes, i.e., positive mode with elongated springs and negative mode with compressed springs. The two prestressed modes enable the frustrated cell with programmable energy landscapes (Fig. 2H). The stored elastic energy is contributed by the stretch of prestressed springs and the deformation of the origami panels and creases. The mountain creases of the Kresling cell shortens when folding is initiated, but the creases return to the initial length at the folded stable state. On the other hand, the deformation of the prestressed springs behaves differently under the two modes. For the negative mode, the prestressed spring has similar kinematics to the mountain crease. The compressed spring is further shortened while the cell is folding. Then, the spring returns to its initial compressed length at the folded stable state. For the positive mode, the spring is elongated at the initial stable state. As

373 the cell folding initiates, the amount of elongation reduces. 435
374 At the folded stable state, the spring returns to its initial 436
375 elongated state. We can see that the deformation history of 437
376 the prestressed spring in the positive mode and negative mode 438
377 is quite different. As a result, the two modes lead to distinct 439
378 shapes of the energy landscape. This observation enriches 440
379 the programmability of the frustrated cells by means of local 441
380 crease control. Moreover, we present an additional local 442
381 frustrated model, i.e., crease rotation, in the SI Appendix, 443
382 section 1, Fig. S2, and Table S3. 444

383 The aforementioned theoretical analysis considers linear 445
384 spring mechanisms with constant stiffnesses, i.e., $k_{s,e} =$ 446
385 *constant* and $k_{r,e} = \textit{constant}$. However, the theoretical 447
386 framework (Eqs. 5-7) can be generalized to incorporate 448
387 nonlinear springs in the frustrated model. We can replace $k_{s,e}$ 449
388 and $k_{r,e}$ with expressions describing the nonlinear behavior of 450
389 the spring elements. More details of the theory for nonlinear 451
390 spring modeling are shown in SI Appendix, section 2, Fig. 452
391 S3, and Table S4. 453

392 **Experimental study on unit cells.** Experiments involve the 454
393 three frustrated models theoretically investigated in the 455
394 previous session. We develop a modular fabrication solution 456
395 to realize the global stretch model, including the spring 457
396 element, the wire connector, 3D-printed frames and handles 458
397 (Fig. 3A, Movie S2). The handle controls the level of prestress 459
398 in the spring element. The spring extension $\Delta\ell$ is a function 460
399 of the radius of the handle r_{handle} and the number of interval 461
400 turns n , defined as follows: $\Delta\ell = n(2\pi r_{\text{handle}})/12$. The 462
401 prestressed spring deforms the standard Kresling into a new 463
402 equilibrium state configuration. This new stable state is 464
403 frustrated as it stores elastic energy in both panels and 465
404 the spring. The amount of energy stored in the frustrated 466
405 model is tunable by controlling the spring extension. In 467
406 the compression experiments with the free-rotating fixture, 468
407 we test three different spring extensions and compare the 469
408 results with those of the standard origami cell (Movie S2). 470
409 Figure 3B reports the experimental results and theoretical 471
410 prediction. For the standard Kresling, we conduct tests on 472
411 five specimens and calculate the mean value (solid curves) 473
412 and the corresponding standard deviation (shaded regions) 474
413 using the formulas in SI Appendix, section 3. For the 475
414 frustrated Kresling, we conduct tests on three specimens 476
415 for each prestressed model. The error bar at the first stable 477
416 state is the standard deviation calculated from the measured 478
417 displacement. 479

418 The strain energy plots (Fig. 3B top-left) confirm that the 480
419 frustrated models have non-zero base energy at the initial 481
420 stable states, and the amount of the base energy depends on 482
421 the spring extensions. Note that we assume that the spring 483
422 elements do not contribute to the energy formulation anymore 484
423 if they are deactivated (i.e., zero prestress). Consequently, 485
424 the behavior of the frustrated cell becomes identical to that 486
425 of the standard cell (Fig. 3B bottom-left). The plots in 487
426 Fig. 3B (right) illustrate the force-displacement relationship 488
427 obtained from both experiment and theory, respectively. We 489
428 zoom in on the initial loading region to show the shift of 490
429 force curves. Both experimental data and theoretical analysis 491
430 verify that the starting point of the force curve shifts as 492
431 the prestress increases. The amount of shift corresponds to 493
432 the height change at the first stable state in the frustrated 494
433 models. Note that the magnitude of the peak force decreases 495
434

435 as more prestress is applied in experiments. In theoretical 436
437 analyses, the peak forces are similar. This discrepancy is 438
439 caused by the panel buckling at initial loading with activated 440
441 frustration (Fig. 3B bottom-right), which is not considered in 442
443 the theoretical analysis (see more discussion in SI Appendix, 444
445 section 4). 446

447 We design a specific mechanism to apply positive prestress 448
449 in the global rotation model. This mechanism, which behaves 450
451 like a torsional spring, involves the customized inclined 452
453 component, the spring element, the wire connector, and 454
455 3D-printed frames and handles (Fig. 3C, Movie S3). The 456
457 handle controls the amount of prestress applied along the 458
459 torsional direction. The torsional angle $\Delta\eta$ and torsional 460
461 stiffness $k_{r,e}$ are defined as: $\Delta\eta = n(2\pi r_{\text{handle}}/r_{\text{frame}})/12$ and 462
463 $k_{r,e} = T/\Delta\eta$, where T is the reaction torque, and r_{frame} is the 464
465 radius of the frame. Compared with the standard cell, the 466
467 prestressed cell is deformed in its initial stable configuration 468
469 with a non-zero base energy. The elastic energy is stored in 469
470 both the deformed panels and the springs. Given a constant 471
472 spring stiffness, the torsional angle controls the magnitude of 472
473 the energy stored in the initial configuration of the frustrated 473
474 model. We test three different angles under torsional loading 474
475 with the free-translating fixture (Movie S3). Both theoretical 475
476 and experimental results (Fig. 3D-left) verify the capability 476
477 of the global rotation model for tuning base energy at initial 477
478 stable states. In addition, the twist angle-torque curves for 478
479 deactivated and activated frustration are different as shown 479
480 in Fig. 3D (right). The zoomed-in plots further illustrate 480
481 the different initial loading points. The shift of those points 481
482 is related to the amount of prestress applied in the global 482
483 rotation frustrated model. 483

484 The two aforementioned global frustrated models incor- 484
485 porate only positive prestresses. In contrast, the crease 485
486 (local) stretch with negative prestress further enhances the 486
487 energy landscape programmability of the frustrated model. 487
488 The crease stretch prototype involves compressed springs 488
489 inserted in 3D-printed cases aside from the mountain creases 489
490 of the cell (Fig. 3E, Movie S4). Due to the prestressed 490
491 spring elements, the frustrated cell gets extended and then 491
492 stays in a new equilibrium state. The new state has a 492
493 non-zero elastic base energy contributed by the deformed 493
494 origami cell and the prestressed spring element. Tuning the 494
495 magnitude of the prestress leads to controllable base energy 495
496 at the initial stable states, as shown in Fig. 3F (top-left). 496
497 Moreover, the experimental results show that the shape of 497
498 the energy landscapes depends on prestress levels of the 498
499 springs. The more the spring element is compressed, the 499
500 higher energy barrier is achieved for the frustrated cell. This 500
501 behavior agrees with the theoretical analysis shown in Fig. 3F 501
502 (bottom-left). Figure 3F (right) verifies that the initial loading 502
503 position of samples with deactivated and achieved frustration 503
504 are different. The initial loading position is related to the 504
505 configuration of the Kresling origami at the first stable state. 505
506 The negative displacement u indicates increased height of the 506
507 origami sample in the frustrated model. On the other hand, 507
508 we validate the crease (local) stretch with positive prestress. 508
509 We refer to SI Appendix, section 5 and Fig. S4 for more 509
510 details. 510

511 **Experimental study on assemblies.** Beyond the studies at 511
512 the unit cell level, we explore the mechanical behavior of 512
513 origami assemblies composed of standard cells and frustrated 513
514 515 516

497 cells. The cells are modular, and they can be connected by
498 miniature neodymium magnets embedded in the frames.

499 **Standard Kresling assemblies.** For an origami array with three
500 standard cells, there are, in total, eight stable states as
501 shown in Fig. 4A. In theory, fifty-six folding paths connect
502 any two stable states. In practice, sixteen out of fifty-six
503 folding paths are unachievable without transiting through
504 other stable states (Fig. 4B). For instance, state I (with
505 all three cells deployed) cannot deform directly to state
506 VIII (with all three cells folded) unless passing through the
507 other states where one or two cells have been folded. Note
508 that eight additional paths in Fig. 4C are infeasible due
509 to the intrinsic energy barrier ΔU built in the three cells,
510 i.e., $\Delta U(\text{red cell}) > \Delta U(\text{yellow cell}) \approx \Delta U(\text{blue cell})$, which are
511 differentiated by controlling the panel thickness (see details
512 in Materials and Methods). Moreover, state VIII cannot be
513 pulled to state V because lower-energy barrier cells (blue
514 or yellow) must deploy before the higher-energy barrier cell
515 (red). As a result, only thirty-two out of fifty-six folding
516 paths are feasible (Fig. 4D). Eight feasible paths have been
517 verified experimentally under two types of loading conditions:
518 axial loading and torsional loading (Movie S5, details in
519 Movie S5 are shown in SI Appendix, section 6 and Fig. S5).
520 The axial loading condition involves two fixtures, i.e., one
521 is rotationally constrained, and the other one displays free
522 rotation (see more details in SI Appendix, section 7). The
523 corresponding testing results are presented in Fig. 4E. On
524 the other hand, the torsional loading condition is equipped
525 with the axially constrained fixture and the free-translating
526 fixture, respectively. The corresponding experimental data
527 are shown in Fig. 4F. According to the experimental data,
528 we calculate the energy landscapes of eight feasible paths in
529 SI Appendix, section 8 and Fig. S6.

531 **Frustrated Kresling assemblies.** The 3-cell origami assembly
532 shown in Fig. 5A is prestressed such that the top two cells
533 include springs on the mountain creases (local level) and the
534 bottom cell includes a rotational spring (global level). Each
535 of the frustrated cells has two stable states with tunable energy
536 barriers enabled by the prestressing level. As a result, the
537 assembly has, in total, eight stable states, like Fig. 4; however,
538 the behavior is quite different. The frustrated assembly
539 can be continuously reprogrammed by means of local cell
540 control. This reprogrammability leads to precise control
541 of the folding sequences, and enables the eight previously
542 infeasible folding paths of Fig. 4C to be achieved as feasible
543 folding paths in Fig. 5B. For example, although the intrinsic
544 energy barrier of the red cell is bigger than that of the blue
545 cell, the global rotation mechanism actively lowers the red
546 cell energy barrier. Therefore, when state I deforms to state
547 VII following path ①, the frustrated red cell folds while
548 the blue cell remains deployed during the process. The
549 loading condition for this deformation is axial compression
550 with a rotationally constrained fixture, as shown by the green
551 curve in Fig. 5C (Movie S6). The plot has an orange curve,
552 which corresponds to the feasible deformation path ② in
553 Fig. 5B, under axial loading with free-rotating fixture (Movie
554 S6). Other feasible folding paths, i.e., path ③ and path
555 ④, are achieved by torsional loading conditions with the
556 axially constrained fixture and the free-translating fixture,
557 respectively, as shown in Fig. 5D (Movie S6). In addition,

559 energy landscapes corresponding to feasible paths in Fig. 5C
560 and D are presented in SI Appendix, section 8 and Fig. S7.
561 More details of the reprogrammability of the feasible folding
562 paths and energy landscapes are shown in SI Appendix,
563 section 9 and Fig. S8.

564 The results in Fig. 5 demonstrate that the ability to switch
565 among different states, by controlling the prestressing levels,
566 enables the 8 feasible folding paths of Fig. 5B, something not
567 achievable with the non-frustrated Kresling array (Fig. 4).
568 While these folding paths could also be enabled by designing
569 new cells with predefined energy barriers, through material
570 and/or geometry selections, this discrete approach inevitably
571 introduces new infeasible folding paths and does not support
572 in-situ reconfiguration. In contrast, the continuous approach
573 of geometric frustration, combined with a finely tuned spring
574 mechanism, enables the elimination of infeasible folding paths.
575 This allows for dynamic reprogramming of folding behavior
576 within the same array, leading to adaptability and control.

577 **Scope of frustration.** Though our designs of frustration is
578 created based on Kresling origami structure, they can be
579 used to embed frustration into other origami structures. For
580 instance, Figure 6A gives an example to explore the influence
581 of prestressing on a curved-crease origami tube. The states
582 at the red and blue points as well as the force curves indicate
583 that the mechanism with stretching spring causes a shift of
584 initial state of the origami tube. Under axial compression
585 loading, the frustrated curved-crease tube exhibits significant
586 panel buckling (see the state at the blue-star point in Fig. 6A).
587 Moreover, detailed comparison between the frustrated and
588 non-frustrated curved-crease origami is shown in SI Appendix,
589 section 10 and Fig. S9.

590 The second application relates to programmable non-
591 commutative behavior of Kresling arrays (Fig. 6B). We
592 consider a Kresling array consisting of two lower energy
593 barrier cells at the top and one higher energy barrier cell at
594 the bottom, and consider two examples, one that does not
595 involve frustration and one that does. In both examples, we
596 apply counterclockwise twist followed by clockwise twist, and
597 then we reverse the actuation sequence (i.e., clockwise twist
598 followed by counterclockwise twist), always resulting in a total
599 zero net twist at the end of each actuation sequence. For the
600 first example, the array shows history-dependent behavior
601 in the sense that the deformed configuration depends on
602 the sequence of the twist actuation. We demonstrate this
603 feature by experiments on a reference configuration under
604 the actuation sequences described above (Fig. 6B-top). Note
605 that details of the jagged portion on the unloading curve are
606 elaborated in SI Appendix, section 11 and Fig. S10. The
607 two different end configurations demonstrate the relevance of
608 twisting history, which indicates non-commutative behavior.
609 For the example involving frustration, the top unit cell (blue)
610 is the same as before; however, the bottom two cells are
611 frustrated. The middle cell has linear (local) springs (with
612 induced negative prestress) providing it with a higher energy
613 barrier than the top cell. The bottom cell has an especially
614 designed torsional (global) spring (with induced positive
615 prestress) providing it with the highest energy barrier of
616 the assembly. We observe non-commutative state transitions
617 as well (Fig. 6B-bottom); however, comparatively, the two
618 final states in the frustrated Kresling array are different
619 from those in the non-frustrated Kresling array, resulting in
620

a programmable (frustration-dependent) non-commutative state transition.

Furthermore, we create a shape-morphing metamaterial by embedding the spring mechanism into a 3D-printed truss prototype involving multiple Kresling columns (43) (Fig. 6C). The level of prestress in each Kresling column depends on the stiffness of springs. Here, the column 0 has no spring, while the stiffness of the springs in column 1 and column 2 is 0.11N/mm and 0.35N/mm, respectively. All the springs are connected with a handle through wires. Rotating the handle applies a constant stretch to all the springs. Since the spring of column 2 has the highest stiffness, it deforms more than column 1 and column 0 (see Fig. 6C-bottom). As a result, the varying deformation in different columns allows the metamaterial to achieve shape-morphing behavior.

Discussion

We present geometrically frustrated Kresling assemblies with tunable energy landscapes and folding paths. The assembly is modular, and it consists of both standard origami cells and frustrated cells. We introduce frustrated modules with three types of prestress, i.e., global stretch, global rotation, and crease (local) stretch. The prestress of the frustrated model is continuously adjustable by controlling the special springs, which allows for changing the energy barrier for the cell. The theoretical analysis verifies that the energy landscape for the frustrated cells is programmable and the corresponding energy barrier is continuously tunable. We prototype all three types of frustrated origami cells and use four loading and boundary conditions to validate the behavior of the cells experimentally. Experiments demonstrate that activating and deactivating frustration can dramatically enhance the programmability of the origami assembly, unlocking otherwise infeasible folding paths. The present concept can be implemented widely in reconfigurable systems where in-situ programmability is needed in the application, e.g., adaptable metamaterials for shape morphing.

Materials and Methods

Formulation of the frustration theory. Since the frustrated cell can be controlled by both axial force, F , and torque, T , the work done on the cell is calculated by $W(u, \varphi) = \int F du + \int T d\varphi$. The total potential energy of the frustrated cell, Π , can be expressed using the total elastic energy, U_{fru} , and work, W , i.e.,

$$\Pi(u, \varphi) = U_{\text{fru}}(u, \varphi) - W(u, \varphi). \quad [8]$$

Notice that $\Pi(u, \varphi)$ is a function of two independent variables, u and φ . Based on the principle of minimum total potential energy, equilibrium is achieved when $\partial\Pi/\partial u = 0$ and $\partial\Pi/\partial\varphi = 0$. Thus, the axial force, F , and the torque, T , are calculated by:

$$F(u, \varphi) = \frac{\partial U_{\text{fru}}(u, \varphi)}{\partial u}, \quad T(u, \varphi) = \frac{\partial U_{\text{fru}}(u, \varphi)}{\partial \varphi}. \quad [9]$$

Fabrication of Kresling origami cells. Both standard and frustrated origami cells were fabricated by a material composed of multi-layer

origami papers (Tant) and adhesive tapes in between (3M 9474LE, 0.17mm-thick). The crease patterns of the blue and yellow cells include two layers of origami papers and one layer of adhesive tape. The crease pattern of the red cell is made of three layers of origami papers and two layers of adhesive tapes. We cut the mountain creases for all the cells. Additionally, for the crease (local) stretch (Fig. 3E) design, we cut a trapezoid hole on the panel to avoid interaction between the prestressed element and the origami cell. More details are shown in SI Appendix, section 12 and Fig. S11.

Fabrication of 3D-printed truss. The 3D-printed truss model in Fig. 6C consists of two components: rods and soft joints, which are fabricated using a Stratasys J55 Prime polyjet printer. The rods are printed using the VeroWhite material, and the joints are printed using FLXA9950 (Shore-A 50), with a mix of VeroUltraClear and ElasticoClear.

Fabrication of prestressed elements. The 3D printed prestressed components are fabricated using a Stratasys J55 Prime polyjet printer. For the global stretch model, the frames and handle are printed by the VeroWhite material, and the markers are printed by the VeroMagenta material. For the global rotation model, the top frame and markers are fabricated by the same material as the global stretch design, while the bottom frame and handle are printed by the VeroUltraClear material. For the crease (local) stretch model, the frames and markers are printed by the same material as the global stretch one, while the case assembled on the top and bottom frames printed by the VeroYellow and VeroMagenta materials, respectively. The pulley used in the global rotation model is a ball bearing pulley (MiSUMi, SZV3-12). The spring used in the global stretch model is an extension spring (McMaster-Carr, 9065K566). The spring used in the global rotation model is an extension spring (McMaster-Carr, 5108N036). The spring used in the crease (local) stretch model is a compression spring (McMaster-Carr, 9657K641). The springs in the global models are connected to the 3D-printed components using a 0.3 mm diameter fishing wire. More detailed parameters are provided in SI Appendix, section 12. Note that the spring system can be manufactured by standard 3D printers, which enhances the practicality of the frustration concept. For instance, we show an illustration of integrating 3D-printed springs into cell origami in SI Appendix, section 12 and Fig. S12.

Experimental setups. In Fig. 3, we conduct both compression tests and torsion tests on an Instron loading frame machine (Model 68SC-5 Single Column Testing System), equipped with free-rotating and free-translating fixtures, respectively (see more information in SI Appendix, section 12 and Fig. S13). The applied axial load and torque have been measured with a force/torque sensor (Biaxial Load Cell ± 445 N, ± 5.65 Nm). The compression experiments are conducted at a speed of 0.25 mm/s, while the torsional experiments are performed at 0.5 deg/s. In Figs. 4 and 5, we conduct compression tests using both rotationally constrained and free-rotating fixtures. Moreover, we conduct torsion tests using both axially constrained and free-translating fixtures.

Data, Materials, and Software Availability. All data are included in the article and/or supporting information.

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923 **Fig. 2.** Theoretical model of geometrically frustrated Kresling origami cells. (A) Global stretch feature. Standard Kresling origami (top-middle) and two frustrated models (top-left and top-right). The left model has a compressed spring (negative prestress), while the right one has an extended spring (positive prestress). Here, h_0 denotes the height of the standard Kresling cell, h_{fru} is the height of the frustrated cell, and u_0 is the height difference. (B) Reprogrammable energy landscapes (black) versus tunable landscapes (orange) with the negative prestress model. Bottom: intrinsic energy landscape (black) versus tunable landscapes (orange) with the positive prestress model. Left: the elastic energy U versus the normalized axial displacement u/u_m under axial loading with free-rotation. Right: the elastic energy U versus the normalized twist angle φ/φ_m under torsional loading with free-translation. (C) Continuously tunable energy barrier with the global stretch feature. Normalized length changes of the spring $\Delta l_e/u_m$ versus the energy barrier ΔU , which is defined as the maximum energy of a frustrated model U_{max} minus the energy at the first stable state U_{fru}^I . (D) Global rotation feature. Standard Kresling origami (top-middle) and two frustrated models (top-left and top-right). The left model has a deformed torsional spring that rotates the origami clockwise. The right model has a deformed torsional spring that rotates the origami counterclockwise. Here, $\Delta \eta_e$ denotes the rotating angle of the torsional spring. (E) Reprogrammable energy landscapes. (F) Continuously tunable energy barriers for the frustrated model with global rotation. (G-I) Crease (local) stretch feature and the corresponding energy solutions. The symbols b_0 and b_{fru} denote the lengths of mountain creases in the standard and the frustrated model, respectively.

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Fig. 3. Experiments involving the three frustrated models of the previous figure. (A) Global stretch with positive prestress. Top-left: illustration of axial loading with a free-rotating fixture. Top-right: schematic of the design enabling prestress in the axial direction. Bottom-left: photo of an undeformed origami cell. Bottom-right: photo of a prestressed unit in its initial stable state. (B) Experimental results and theoretical predictions. Top: experimental results comparing the behavior of the frustrated models with the standard origami cell. Solid lines represent the mean value and shade regions represent the standard deviation of the experimental data. Bottom: corresponding theoretical predictions. Left: axial displacement u versus stored elastic energy U . Right: displacement versus applied forces F . The insets highlight the early stages of the test. (C) Global rotation with positive prestress. Top-left: illustration of torsional loading with a free-translating fixture. Top-right: schematic of the design with torsional prestress in the cell. Bottom-left: photo of an undeformed origami cell. Bottom-right: photo of a prestressed cell in its initial stable state. (D) Experimental results and theoretical predictions. (E) Crease (local) stretch with negative prestress. Top-left: illustration of the loading with a free-rotating fixture. Top-right: schematic of the compressed springs strategically located along the mountain creases. Bottom-left: photo of an undeformed origami cell. Bottom-right: photo of a prestressed cell in its initial stable state. (F) Experimental results and theoretical predictions.

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Fig. 4. Deformation paths achieved on 3-cell standard Kresling assembly under four loading conditions. The intrinsic energy barriers (ΔU) have been selected such that $\Delta U(\text{red cell}) > \Delta U(\text{yellow cell}) \approx \Delta U(\text{blue cell})$. The yellow and blue cells have opposite chiralities. (A) Stable states. (B) Unachievable folding paths. (C) Infeasible folding paths. (D) Feasible folding paths. (E) Experimental results associated to rotationally constrained fixture and free-rotating fixture. The circled numbers in the plot correspond to those in panel (D). (F) Experimental results associated to axially constrained fixture and free-translating fixture. The circled numbers in the plot correspond to those in panel (D).

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Fig. 5. Deformation paths achieved on 3-cell frustrated Kresling assembly under four loading conditions. The energy barriers of the frustrated cells (ΔU_{tru}) have been controlled such that $\Delta U_{tru}(\text{red cell}) < \Delta U_{tru}(\text{yellow cell}) \approx \Delta U_{tru}(\text{blue cell})$. The yellow and blue cells have opposite chiralities. (A) Stable states. (B) Feasible folding paths, which were infeasible in the previous figure. (C) Experimental results associated to rotationally constrained fixture and free-rotating fixture. The circled numbers in the plot correspond to those in panel (B). (D) Experimental results associated to axially constrained fixture and free-translating fixture. The circled numbers in the plot correspond to those in panel (B). The experimental result of path ④ is the same as displayed in Fig. 1.

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Fig. 6. Scope of frustration. (A) Frustrated curved-crease origami structure. Left: photos of the non-frustrated curved-crease origami, the frustrated curved-crease origami, and the buckled curved-crease origami, respectively. Right: experimental data of non-frustrated and frustrated curved-crease origami structures. (B) Programmable non-commutative states enabled by frustration. Top: folding paths and corresponding twist angle vs. torque curves for the non-frustrated Kresling array. Bottom: folding paths and corresponding twist angle vs. torque curves for the frustrated Kresling array. ccw, counterclockwise twist; cw, clockwise twist. (C) Shape-morphing metamaterial with controllable frustration. Top: 3D-printed truss model embedded with different springs. The stiffness of the springs in column 1 and column 2 is 0.11N/mm and 0.35N/mm, respectively. Bottom: deformed configurations for different amounts of prestress applied in the springs.